

Development and Initial Validation of the School Characteristics Checklist in Bangalore City

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=Abstract

School data is vital for identifying problems early and implementing awareness and intervention programs. Schools in India vary in various features such as their governing body, management type, board affiliation, number of grades, teaching medium, infrastructure, and facilities, etc. These heterogeneous characteristics, when included in a sample, lead to measurement errors and ultimately unclear conclusions. The school characteristics checklist outlines certain features of schools, which can be used to determine a homogeneous sample. The development of a school characteristics checklist and its content validity using expert judgment is reported in this article. The administration of the validated checklist among schools in urban Bengaluru is described. The checklist is easy to use, reduces confounding variables, and minimizes measurement errors. It makes the data collection method more scientific, structured, and reduces bias. Researchers conducting studies among school students, teachers, and school authorities can use the checklist to make their sample more representative. Scope for improvement includes establishing criterion-related validity, construct validity and reliability.

Keywords: Checklist, Content validity, India, School Characteristics

Schools are considered the most important research sites for collecting public health data. This data is analyzed and utilized to promote health-related information, prevent ill health in high-risk schools, and implement interventions. Several researchers collect data from schools because it is “cost-effective and time-efficient”. However, the disadvantage of such a sample is its heterogeneity. In Karnataka alone, there are 44,615 government schools (Government of Karnataka, 2018, May 29) and around 17,000 authorized private schools (Choudhary, 2024). All these schools vary based on their governing body, medium of instruction, management type, board affiliation, number of grades, teaching and learning strategies, infrastructure, and facilities. When data from such a diverse sample is tested or compared, there are sampling errors, and hence, findings cannot be generalized to the population.

To offset this disadvantage and create homogeneous school samples, schools need to be matched for certain characteristics before being compared or tested. In other words, schools are controlled to include only certain aspects or features. Hence, the data collected from a controlled pool makes a homogeneous sample. This way, the findings have a chance of generalizability. Most researchers use the homogeneous convenient sampling to limit the school sample to a certain socio-demographic factor, for example, socio-economic status, ethnicity, or gender. The larger the number of homogeneous factors, the more homogeneous the sample will be (Jager et al., 2017).

Checklists can be utilized to create a homogeneous school data sample. Checklists are formal tools that provide a framework of relevant criteria. These criteria are used mindfully during certain research processes for inclusion or evaluation (Schmutz et al., 2014). A researcher uses the checklist to choose from already defined school-related items and response types to create the sample. The criteria in a checklist become the bare minimum requirement for a school to be qualified for a research study. (Stufflebeam, 2021). This article aims to describe the checklist development process and to establish its content validity. The checklist development process includes defining the variables, pooling items, creating an expert committee, obtaining their ratings, reaching a consensus for the final list of items, and calculating the “content validity index”. The final validated checklist will improve the methodology of the larger research study. It will provide objectivity, impartiality, reduce bias,

and improve the reliability and reproducibility of the conclusions. It will also reduce any halo effect, a kind of bias where one feature of a school is generalized to other schools. It will also minimize confirmation bias, where schools are approached based on the researcher's subjective perception or fondness for the school (Jager et al., 2017).

Literature Review

A review of previous literature refers to a compilation of all the previous work done in the field of a particular topic. This compilation, when done critically, assists in identifying gaps in the previous work. The literature reviewed for this article consists of research articles regarding checklist development and established schools' related checklists in India.

2.1 Process in Checklist Development

Schmutz (2014) enlisted steps in creating checklists. The five steps to systematically develop a checklist are: to create a draft of the items in the checklist; share the draft with experts who then review it, and after multiple rounds, a consensus is reached about the final list of items. The third round is to finalize the items, organize them, and conduct a pilot study. Items that are vague and irrelevant must be removed. Step four is that the final checklist is shared with experts to delete, edit, and modify the final items. The final step is to establish important and less important items. The final checklist is shared with experts again, who only rate items as important or less important. This step also includes establishing the reliability and validity of the checklist.

Asperanti (2011) formed a checklist to audit crisis plans in schools. In the light of many tragedies in schools off late including bomb scares, violence, natural disasters, it is evident that all schools must have a crisis plan checklist for prevention (accident prevention, suicide prevention, bullying prevention, violence prevention), intervention (crime plan, plan for death occurring in school, bombing plan, plan in case of kidnap) and postvention (procedure of informing caregivers, media, counselling facilities, emergency phone numbers). The authors expanded the "brief crisis plan checklist" by Saxon and Bain (1998) to include relevant items and conducted an inter-rater reliability test to standardize the checklist. In the pilot, the authors recruited two graduate students to compare the crisis plan of seven schools with the newly created checklist. Cohen's coefficient was also identified. The inter-rater agreement ranged

from 79.22% and 87.01% and the coefficient values ranged between .35 and .73, indicating moderate levels of agreement.

Lane et al (2021) created a checklist named the “Observational School Environment Checklist”. It was a checklist developed to audit if children are getting opportunities to eat healthy food and perform physical activities within their school. The checklist was developed by adapting pre-existing tools and testing them in eighteen schools. Four locations across schools were chosen (canteen, lobby, gym, and outdoor), and items for four domains were listed (attractiveness, atmosphere, accessibility, and advertising). Item responses were binary-yes (1) and no (0). The testing included two raters independently rating the items and resolving disagreements on any items. The percentage of agreements was calculated along with Cohen’s Kappa to ascertain its reliability. All agreement scores were within the acceptable range (72.3% for attractiveness, 86.3%-97.1% for atmosphere, 82.9%- 100% for accessibility, and 92.9% for advertising), and kappa scores were well within the standards (0.66-0.91 for atmosphere, 0.60-1.00 for accessibility, 0.46 for attractiveness, and 0.77 for advertising).

Hong et al (2020) developed a checklist for “meaningful learning in classroom observation”. The three-pillar theory of teaching competence (“pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, and technological pedagogical content knowledge”) was the theoretical basis for pooling items for the checklist. The items were revised by three professors of education followed by three school principals to establish content validity. A thorough four round review was conducted to assess if respective items were complete and appropriate and for the rational allotment of items to domains and the readability of these items. Reviews and corrections included for language fluency and alignment of text. Finally, five teachers were recruited to assess the checklist and its applicability in real classroom settings.

Tadema et al (2005) brought together a checklist of child characteristics in an inclusive setting. Since in an inclusive school, children have diverse learning and developmental problems with varying degrees of severity, a checklist was warranted. The checklist items measure how to assess differently abled children in inclusive schools. To create the items, the “International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health” (ICF) was referred. Domains that were relevant to the checklist were chosen, namely, general information, function, activities, and participation. The response ranged from ‘yes, independent’ to ‘no, not even with full support’. The draft was given to nine professionals who rated the items for

content, difficulty, overlap, and relevance. Based on their feedback, items were deleted, edited, or added. To establish reliability, two teachers independently used the checklist to assess 10 students, and inter-rater reliability was calculated using the agreement percentage method. The agreement percentages ranged between 0.80 and 0.86, which are acceptable. The checklist can be used to identify the special needs of a child, to determine which grade might be suitable for the child, what the classroom requirements might be for the child, and to track progress through the school years (Tadema et al., 2005).

Studies in this section provide clarity on the methodology to develop a sound checklist. Asperanti (2011) and Lane (2021) used already existing tools to create their checklist. Hong et al. (2020) and Tadema (2005) developed their checklist based on theories and frameworks. Since school characteristics are not an established construct in educational psychology/school psychology, it was clear that developing items for the checklist would have to rely on relevant recommendations by educational boards that dictate schools in their formation and administration. The next section includes a review of the various frameworks provided by different education boards and government education departments.

2.2 School-based checklists in India

Basic sanitation checklist by the Government of India as part of the School Health Program called “Swachhata Action Plan” is a checklist for maintaining cleanliness in schools (Ministry of Education, 2014). The WASH protocol includes pointers for “safe handling of drinking water, sanitation, food hygiene, menstrual hygiene, and waste management”. These are performance indicators of a school, as well as part of the basic life skills curriculum for students.

“School Quality Assessment and Assurance” (2023) by the Central Board of Secondary Education provides a school improvement framework with seven key domains. It expects all CBSE schools to undertake a self-assessment on the domains of “curriculum, infrastructure, inclusive practices, human resources, management and governance, leadership, and student satisfaction”. Under infrastructure, subdomains of activities and provisions provided by the school are listed. Schools must submit documents supporting these subdomains every year, and in turn, the board provides schools with a performance review. Schools get a rating between level 1, indicating ‘inception or low level’, to level 4, indicating a ‘dynamic/evolving’ level.

Accessibility Audit checklist by CBSE board (Accessibility Code for Educational Institutions, 2021) enlists items to identify physical, informational, and emergency barriers in the daily functioning of a school. It can be conducted by the staff of the school, by parents, or by auditors. The checklist audit includes items on how the external environment of the school must be, including footpath handrails and main gate for existing buildings, as well as for new construction. It provides guidelines to remove physical barriers by building ramps and to remove information barriers by having signage.

“The Annual Status of Education Report” (ASER), is a rural household survey generated every year by Pratham publications. A part of this survey is the school Observation sheet that is used to collect data from government schools in villages by trained volunteers. Several criteria are included in the school observation sheet, including number of enrollments, attendance, medium of instruction, number of teachers, number of trainings, variety of facilities, toilets, and grants (ACER, 2024).

“The Comprehensive Child Safety Checklist” is part of the “Manual on Safety and Security of Children in Schools” developed by the “National Commission for Protection of Child Rights (NCPCR)”. It includes instruction on broad domains of infrastructure, psychosocial safety, health, and hygiene. Under these broad domains, checklists for fire safety, sanitation, infrastructure safety, disability access, and safety in grounds and playgrounds are included. The checklist includes specific pointers on “disaster preparedness”, “emergency services”, “anti-bullying”, and “prevention of abuse and exploitation” (NCPCR, 2021).

A safety audit was conducted by NIMHANS in collaboration with Underwriters Laboratories on 131 private schools in August 2019. The survey included schools in Bengaluru and Kolar. It was reported that only 50% of schools met the safety standards. 173 roads leading to these 131 schools did not have signage, speed limits, and designated zones for pick up and drop off (UL Research Institute, July 28, 2020). In view of this finding, the Department of Public Instruction worked on a 25-item checklist addressing infrastructure safety, hygiene, fire safety, and food inspection. A total of 24000 schools have been surveyed using this checklist since August 2025. Headmasters of these schools are instructed to update their school’s status on the Students Achievement Tracking System (SATS) portal daily (Ravishankar, August 5, 2025)

In India, there are recognized guidelines for school improvement, school safety, and sanitation. However, currently, there is a lack of checklists that would assist researchers in creating a homogeneous pool of matched schools to conduct research, specifically in the field of educational or school psychology. The current paper attempts to fill this knowledge gap by creating the School Characteristics Checklist. The objectives of this study are: (i) to pool items for the school characteristics checklist; (ii) to validate its content using the expert judgment method; and (iii) to administer the validated checklist on schools in urban Bangalore to create a homogeneous school sample.

Method

3.1 Defining the Construct and Item Pooling

The construct of School Characteristics is a set of features that define a school. The characteristics, in other words, create an identity for the school. The checklist of these characteristics is meant to help researchers identify schools with similar characteristics. A pool of similar schools then allows the researcher to create a homogeneous sample for research purposes.

The list of school characteristics was created by pooling items from the websites of schools and various education boards (Karnataka State, CBSE, ISCSE). Features that make up the characteristics of a school include board affiliation, management type, size and facilities at school, years in education, the pass percentage every year, and the opportunities children get in activity participation. Some of these are mandated by school education policies and board affiliations (Karnataka Educational Institutions Rules, 2020) and some are expected by parents, for example, bus facilities, meals, etc. The initial 19-item list of the School Characteristics checklist is mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1

Initial items in the School Characteristics Checklist

1	Name of the School
2	Address of the School
3	School Registration Number
4	What is the land size of the school?
5	Is the school located in one campus? a. Yes b. No c. Any other? -----
6	Number of students in the school from 1 st to 10 th grade? [options a and b will be grouped to define “unpopulated school” and options c and d will be grouped to define “populated school”] a. < 300 b. 301-599 c. 600-1000 d. >1000
7	What is the class-size (approximately) in the school? [options a and b will be grouped to define “unpopulated class” and options c and d will be grouped to define “populated class”] a) 0-25 b) 0-35 c) 0-45 d) >45
8	Does the school have nursery to grade 10? a. Yes b. No
9	Does the school have primary, middle and high school in the same premises? a. Yes b. No
10	Which curriculum does the school follow? a. State Board b. Central Board (CBSE / ICSE) c. International Board d. Any others?
11	The mode of instruction in the school is a. English b. Kannada c. Both Any others? -----
12	The school is run by ----- a. Government (education department/social welfare/local government) b. Private (religious group/trust/independent person) c. Any others? -----

13	No. of years the school has completed? [Option a will be considered as “young school” and option b will be considered as “experienced school”] a) < 10 years b) >11 years
14	How is the accessibility to the school? a. Easy b. Difficult c. Reasons -----
15	What is the socio-economic status (SES) of most parents? a. Upper SES b. Middle SES c. Lower SES
16	What are the annual fees (approximately) of the school for middle school? [options a and b are defined “affordable school” and options c and d are defined “premium school”] a. None b. < 1 lakh c. 1- 3 lakh d. >3 lakh
17	How was the school’s performance last year? a. High performance (>97% pass percentage) b. Average Performance (Between 95-97% pass percentage) c. Low Performance (Below 95% pass percentage)
18	Which of the following facilities are provided by the school? [16 out of 24 to qualify] a. Toilet (boys/girls) b. Drinking water c. Canteen d. Mid-day meals e. Electricity f. Play-ground g. Sports facilities h. Extracurricular activities ----- (mention) i. Ramps j. Library k. Reading room l. Compound wall m. Scholarships n. Fee discount o. board p. benches q. textbooks r. uniform s. identity card t. stationary items u. security staff v. mentoring

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> w. counselling x. Internet Connection
19	<p>Does the school have the following activities? [6 out of 8 to qualify]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Parent-teacher meeting/interaction b. Annual day c. Sports day d. Field trips e. Art & craft classes f. Assembly g. Fest h. Inter-house activities

3.2 Establishing Content Validity

To ascertain that the checklist includes relevant items, it was validated using expert judgment. Martínez & Montoya (2020) mention that when experts provide their opinion, judgment, assessment, information, and evidence, it refers to the validation process. They describe an expert as someone with a good background in the field of study and who is acknowledged by others as an expert in that field. Yusoff (2019) recommends that the number of experts should be above six and less than ten for content validation.

“Bronfenbrenner’s Ecological Systems theory” (Paquette & Ryan, 2001) was used as a framework to choose the experts. Teachers and parents form the microsystem of the child; counsellors and school Principals would represent the mesosystem of the child. Teachers with a postgraduate degree and parents with school-going children were part of the expert team. A school counselor’s perspective and a school principal’s opinion were also included in the expert committee.

Based on the number of years of experience and educational qualification, 13 experts were approached, all of whom provided their consent to review the items. Two experts were removed because their educational background was lower than post-graduation, and two were removed because they had less than five years of parenting/ teaching experience. The final nine experts met the criteria for educational background, and parenting/teaching experience. Table 2 shows the profile of the final experts recruited for the validation of the items.

Table 2

Expert's Profile

Name	Expertise	Educational Qualification	Experience in teaching/parenting
Expert 1	Teacher	Post-graduation and above	>11 years
Expert 2	Parent	Post-graduation and above	6-10 years
Expert 3	Teacher	Post-graduation and above	>11 years
Expert 4	Parent	Post-graduation and above	6-10 years
Expert 5	Teacher	Post-graduation and above	>11 years
Expert 6	School Counsellor	Post-graduation and above	>11 years
Expert 7	School Founder & Principal	Post-graduation and above	>11 years
Expert 8	Parent	Post-graduation and above	6-10 years
Expert 9	Teacher	Post-graduation and above	>11 years

3.2.1 Procedure

To determine the content validity of the School Characteristics Checklist. A three-part form mentioning the purpose of the checklist, the reason for choosing them as an expert, and informed consent was shared with experts. Demographic details about age, gender, education, and experience were asked. The last section had the items and rating options. They were asked to rate the items on the level of relevance (one- item is not relevant to school characteristics; two- item is somewhat relevant to school characteristics; three- item is quite relevant to school characteristics; four- item is highly relevant to school characteristics). The experts provided their critiques and suggestions at the end of the rating. Obtained ratings of three and four were coded as one and obtained ratings of one and two were coded as zero. Post-coding, a “content validity index” (Yusoff, 2019) was calculated for each item level and scale level. Apart from quantitatively rating each item, experts also reviewed some of the qualitative aspects such as grammar, sentence structure, syntax, semantics and punctuation in each item.

To determine the absolute passing score on performance items. Items 18 and 19 were school performance-based items. Items 18 and 19 include a list of school facilities and activities, respectively. “The simplified Angoff method” (Direct or yes-no method) was employed to empirically determine the pass score percent for both items (Ricker,2006). Five of the nine experts were telephonically contacted (four experts were not available for the follow-up) with a follow-up question to identify the standard performance required by a school. They were asked, “Will an ordinary/average school have this facility/activity”? They were expected to respond with a simple yes or no for each one of the facilities and activities that the author enumerated. Response ‘Yes’ was coded one, and response ‘No’ was coded zero. A raw passing score and a passing score percent were calculated to establish the absolute passing score for each item (Downing et al., 2006).

To utilize the validated checklist to create a homogeneous sample of schools. The validated checklist was used to create a homogeneous sample of schools for doctoral research purposes. 22 schools were approached to seek permission to conduct the doctoral research. When permissions were sought, the researcher screened the schools using the School Characteristics checklist. Schools that qualified for the checklist were included in the sample. A total of eight schools qualified for the screening and were part of a homogeneous sample for the larger study. The rest of the schools did not meet the passing score on the performance items and were hence eliminated from the sample.

Results

The following are the results of the content validity index and the pass percentage for two checklist items.

Table 3 presents the item numbers, expert scores, and experts in agreement for each item, the item-wise Content Validity Index (I-CVI), and the Scale-level Content Validity Index (S-CVI). Lynn (1986) advocates that CVI should be more than 0.78. Item 2 (Address of the School), Item 3 (school registration number), Item 12 (The school is run by government/private/others), Item 13 (the number of years the school has completed), and Item 17 (How was the school’s performance last year?) do not fulfill the CVI norm criteria. 14 out of the 19 items have obtained acceptable values. Scale level CVI (S-CVI) was found to be 0.95 (after removing items 2, 3, 12, 13, and 17). According to Polit et al. (2006), one must aim for

a scale level of CVI to be equal to or more than 0.90. The obtained S-CVI meets this desirable standard.

The experts provided their suggestions to improve the checklist. Under item 18, the options of hostel/residential facility, right to information provision, medical room facility, CCTV facility, and transportation facility provided by the school were added to the final School Characteristics Checklist. Two experts suggested adding an item- “What is the student-teacher ratio in a class?” to the final School Characteristics Checklist. Grammatical and semantic issues in the checklist were resolved. The total items for the School Characteristics Checklist is 15, with the removal of five items (due to CVI cut-off) and the addition of one new item.

Table 3

Item-Wise and Scale-Level Content Validity Index

Var.	Exp 1	Exp. 2	Exp. 3	Exp. 4	Exp. 5	Exp. 6	Exp. 7	Exp. 8	Exp. 9	Exp in agreement	I-CVI
I 1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 2*	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	7	0.77
I 3*	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	5	0.5
I 4	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	8	0.8
I 5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	8	0.8
I 6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 10	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 11	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 12*	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	7	0.77
I 13*	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	6	0.6
I 14	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 15	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	8	0.8
I 16	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 17*	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	7	0.77
I 18	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
I 19	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	1
Raw Sum=											13.4
S-CVI Raw sum/number of items (items 2, 3, 12, 13, and 17 excluded)											0.95

Note. *Do not meet criteria according to CVI norms, Exp=Expert, CVI= Content Validity Index

“The simplified Angoff method” (Direct or yes-no method) was calculated to obtain the pass percent for items 18 and 19. The raw passing score for item 18 (facilities) is 15.8, and the passing score percent is 65.8%. The raw passing score for item 19 (activities) is 5.6, and the passing score percentage is 70%. To create a homogeneous pool, the school would have to score the same or higher than the passing score on both items in order to be included in the sample.

The validated School Characteristics Checklist was administered in schools in Bengaluru to create a homogeneous sample as part of a large PhD study. Initially, 22 schools were approached for permission to conduct the study. 12 schools gave permission, and they were screened using the School Characteristics Checklist. Eight schools are qualified to be part of the homogeneous sample. The profiles of the schools are mentioned in percentages in Table 4. All qualified schools are standalone schools with no branches, having grades from first to tenth and primary, middle, and high school departments in the same premises. 100% of the schools obtained a score of 65.8 % or above in the performance item-facilities (item 18) available in the school. 100% of the schools obtained a score of 70% and above in the performance item- activities (item 19) offered in the school. 100% of the schools had easy accessibility. The schools were able to understand all the items in the checklist. The respondents (headmaster/principal) were able to identify the purpose of its usage and found the items relevant. Therefore, no further revision was done to the checklist.

Table 4

Profile of Schools that qualified using the School Characteristics Checklist

Characteristics	Percentages
School population	62.5% unpopulated
Classroom population	75% unpopulated classrooms
Board Affiliation	75% - state board; 25% CBSE board
Medium of Instruction	50% Kanada; 50% English
Socio-Economic Status	75 % - low Socio-Economic Status; 25% - middle Socio-Economic Status
Annual Fees	75 % affordable
School performance	87.5% high performance
Teacher-Student ratio	62.5% student-teacher ratio of 30:1

Discussion

In school psychology literature, school characteristics are not an established construct. In this process, the first step was to clarify the construct and purpose of the checklist (Stufflebeam, 2021). The checklist is a list of characteristics of a school. Schools with similar characteristics will allow a researcher to create a homogeneous sample for research purposes. The items were pooled from existing guidelines provided by educational boards. Checklists established by the Ministry of Education (2014), the School Quality Assessment and Assurance by the CBSE board were thoroughly reviewed to pool the items for the School Characteristics Checklist. Additionally, the Accessibility Code for Educational Institutions (2021) by the CBSE board, and the “Manual on Safety and Security of Children in Schools” developed by the “National Commission for Protection of Child Rights” were examined critically for items that would align with the School Characteristics construct. Items that would help a researcher include or exclude a particular school from the sample, qualified for the checklist. Items included identifiers such as the school’s name, location/branches, board affiliation, and language of instruction. School strength, class strength, number of grades, types of departments, accessibility to the school, SES of families enrolled, annual fees, facilities available, and activities offered were some of the descriptive items pooled. Items that were related to other constructs, such as “school safety” and “school sanitation,” did not qualify for the checklist. After this rigorous process, the first draft of the school characteristics checklist included 19 items.

The second objective of the study was to obtain the content validity for the School Characteristics Checklist. The Expert Judgment method was used. When data is limited and a new tool is being constructed, expert judgment provides clarity and certainty (Kirkwood & Bunch, 2017). The judgment of nine diverse (teachers, parents, school counsellor, school principal) experts with post-graduate or higher degrees and more than five years of teaching or parenting experience identified items that were not relevant to the construct. The demographics of experts align with the opinion of Cabero-Almenara & Llorente Cejudo (2013), who recommend that the selection of experts must be based on their qualifications and experience. The “content validity index”, or CVI, was utilised to decide which items were to be retained and which were to be eliminated based on the agreement scores between the experts. According to Gilbert and Prion (2016), CVI is a good statistical method to employ to validate items

numerically. The experts did not agree on five items, and hence, the obtained CVI for the five items did not meet the criteria. The experts also suggested additional facilities under item 18 and an additional item on the teacher-student ratio. The final validated school characteristics checklist includes 15 items after the expert judgement process. The expert judgement method assisted in showing that the items represent the construct of the School Characteristics Checklist. Their appraisal has created clear and precise items that a researcher can use to create a homogeneous sample of schools.

The validated checklist was used to screen schools in the Bengaluru urban area to create a homogenous sample for a larger doctoral study. Schools were screened by asking the headmaster/principal about unobservable items, and the researcher self-reported the observable items. The schools included in the sample were not based on convenience but were more methodical. This makes the data collection method more scientific and less biased. The data analysed from this sample will have minimal confounding variables and minimal measurement errors. The respondents found the checklist easy to use. The construct and language used was easily comprehensible.

Strengths and Limitations

With acceptable content validity ratios, the School Characteristics Checklist has the foundations of a sound tool. It is useful for researchers in the field of public health, school psychology, educational psychology, and social psychology. However, the current version lacks criterion-related validity, construct validity and reliability. Despite these limitations, the checklist is a practical way to quickly and economically screen schools to obtain a representative and homogenous sample. The checklist has academic and practical utility and can help other scholars to engage with school teachers, students, and administrators.

Conclusion

In an urban city like Bangalore, there are numerous schools. Each school is different in size, varied by the curriculum and activities it provides, and diverse in the medium of instruction and class size. Any research scholar would find it challenging to analyze data collected from such a varied sample. For this practical knowledge gap, a list of school characteristics was created and validated. The final School Characteristic Checklist has 15 items that can be used to filter heterogeneous schools to create a homogeneous sample. Overall,

the items measure the intended School Characteristics construct and has practical utility for researchers.

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